

ANCIENT CHINESE PEARLS

Khalil Kudratovich Soatov

Authors: Candidate of Economics

Nuriddin Boymatov

teacher of Guzor Industrial and Transport Technical College

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7614867>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 25-yanvar 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 04-fevral 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 07-fevral 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Green place, city block, premises, public, pearl mulberry, caronaverus, grippe.

ABSTRACT

The nationwide project "Green Place" announced in our country is very important. Practical work in this regard is being actively carried out under the initiative of the Honorary Public Council of the Chugurtma Mahalla People's Assembly of Ghuzar District. In particular, the ancient Khuzor (now Guzor) Chinese pearl mulberry trees in the yard of Khojabash father's shrine are the center of attention of many people. Our opinion will become clearer if we refer to the stories about this, which have been passed down from generation to generation in the memories of the elderly people of Chogurtma village.

Annotation. The nationwide project "Green Place" announced in our country is very important. Practical work in this regard is being actively carried out under the initiative of the Honorary Public Council of the Chugurtma Mahalla People's Assembly of Ghuzar District. In particular, the ancient Khuzor (now Guzor) Chinese pearl mulberry trees in the yard of Khojabash father's shrine are the center of attention of many people. Our opinion will become clearer if we refer to the stories about this, which have been passed down from generation to generation in the memories of the elderly people of Chogurtma village.

Key words: Green place, city block, premises, public, pearl mulberry, caronaverus, grippe.

This ancient pearl mulberry tree, which you see, had a circumference of ten meters, and its height was the same in ancient times, and it has reached eight meters. This is a family tree of a pair of mulberry trees, our ancestors told us that it goes back to the secrets of the creation of the universe system, says Bakhrom Kamolov, the chief supervisor of the Khujabash father's shrine.

This ancient mulberry, with the authenticity of its remains, makes the ancient Khuzar a contender for entering the book of Genis with its age and antiquity, as well as the greatness of its body. It passes through India, Bakteria and Sugd, as well as Chin-Mochin and Chin-Sugd, connecting East and West, Almashinuv, Darvesh and Shokhuli, the central intersection of the Great Silk Caravan Road, and according to the legends of the local population, there is another secret road from this address, which is opposite Kabatulla. From the qibla side, the paths of arrival of Turk (Chin), the youngest son of Nuh alayhsalam, are echoing from the mosque.

If we look into the distant past, we can see that mulberry trees have been planted at the intersections of caravan roads, near luxury buildings, temples, and canals, in places where people live.

Since the mulberry tree is resistant to high and low water, it penetrated the lower part of the buildings with its strong roots and served to eliminate the water and preserve the building for a long time. However, the role of mulberry in human life is very big. There have been many cases of people surviving by eating mulberry fruit, making raisins and molasses during drought, famine and war.

White Chinese mulberry is described as "Pearl mulberry" in our people, making a very beautiful analogy. In fact, white mulberry is reminiscent of pearl grains.

In fact, "Marvarid Tut" has many useful aspects for humans.

Mulberry has been used since ancient times as a remedy against upper respiratory tract diseases, coughs and colds. The famous doctor Husayn Sherozi described that "Mulberry produces clean blood in the human body, gives energy to the brain, opens the knots in the organs, improves the work of the liver and spleen, and it also drives urine."

Everyone knows that today mulberry leaves are widely used to feed silkworms. It is noteworthy that Khuzor Chin pearl mulberry is very resistant to cold and drought. This variety is mainly propagated by grafting. The fruit is eaten fresh and dried. They also prepared mulberry holva and molasses from it. In ancient times, the Khuzar market was visited, and caravans took this fruit and its products from these destinations.

In most markets these days, we can't even find these products in daylight. We rush to the pharmacy because of coronavirus, flu, cold, but we don't pay attention to the simple and cheap treatment. We build luxurious buildings, we wish to have seven roses, but for some reason we do not plant two mulberries nearby. Do you know why most mulberries are planted on the steps of all the saints? Because our people showed special love to this tree and held it dear as it "gives both food and clothing".

Until the time of the former Soviet Union, in the ancient village of Chugurtma, silk yarn was spun and woven, and the name of the village came from this. It would be an excellent light upon light if we teach our youth about this issue again.

You can see in the photo a relic of the real pearl mulberry of ancient Khuzar, which gives sweet fruits to pilgrims every year in the courtyard of the shrine.

By the way, if we study the situation of Marvarid mulberries in Chugurtma village from the eighteenth century to the sixties of the twentieth century, a lot becomes clear.

The above Buzrukvor was sent to Katta Mahalla, Patron village of Beshkent, on the western side of the huge mulberry tree, in the beginning of the eighteenth century, by the order of the emir of Bukhara, to Mullah Sher Khuzor, who was a descendant of "Ahli Kalam". In turn, he was given twelve parcels of land from Katta mahala of Chugurtma, and each parcel was planted with fruit seedlings and crops brought in caravans from different countries.

Word of mouth sources say that Mulla Sher planted local real mulberry trees around the paykals and began to take good care of the old ones. These generations of people were fluent in several languages - that is, Pashtun, Persian, Russian, Arabic, Chinese. They brought their relatives who knew the language to the village and went on a commercial trip with caravans. He also built a new mosque in the neighborhood.

The interesting thing is, as my grandfather heard from his grandfather, the example of the garden created by Mulla Sher reminds me of the garden of the era, and if you lick the real pearl mulberry molasses prepared by him, it will crack your tongue. The older generation of the village still talk about it among themselves. Mulla Sher planted the seedlings in the homes of residents of Juvazkhana, Katta, Chuqir, Kertagan, and Abulais neighborhoods. The next generation of the dynasty, Vokhabek, also carried out these works. It is said that he was the head of such good deeds many times when he worked as a devanbeg of the Khuzar tribe.

There is a saying in our people that "Knowledge and power are twins". Another great service of Voshabek is that during the Shahrissabz governorship, he took with him Chugurtma merchants, caravanners, forward-thinking, brave soldiers and warriors. And he opened a new type of school and taught foreign languages to their children. One of them, Gulmurad (1906-1944), the son of merchant, caravan owner Normomin, son of Normurod, born in Shahrissabz, mastered Arabic, Persian, and Russian languages in Shahrissabz school. During the time of the Soviets, he founded the first Raiza (agricultural products) office of Guzor, the development of Katta Mahalla as a village. He even managed to save his fellow villagers from eavesdropping.

He was the head of Boisun district party

organization. In Samarkand, he took an active part in the creation of the military district of Turkestan, the formation of military units in the country during the years of the Great Patriotic War, and even shed blood in the battles of the Second World War. He organized a partisan movement in the lands occupied by the enemy and sacrificed his life for the Motherland. Therefore, I think that now is the time to illuminate and study the life path of Guzor Chekist Gulmurad Normurodov, who was forgotten like a pearl.

The place of each nation in the general scale of development is determined by the level of spirituality achieved by the intelligentsia of that nation. From this point of view, another honorable person of Guzar, Abdulla Fattaev, grandson of Vokhabek, is considered one of the Chogurtma clans.

References:

1. B. A. Ahmedov. Historical sources of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: "Teacher". 2001.- Pages 13-20.
2. T. S. Saidkulov. The peoples of Central Asia are famous for their history. - Tashkent: "Teacher". 1993. – pp. 3-9.
3. Collection of oriental manuscripts of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. History Composers D. Yu. Yusupova, R.P. Jalilova. -Tashkent: "Fan". 1998. -S. 3-7.
4. A manuscript book in the cultures of the peoples of the East. Book one.-Moscow: "Science". 1987.-S.5-17.
5. Collection of reports from Manbashunoslamk. Composer A. A. Madraimov.-T.: TDPU. 2001. - pp. 10-18.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY